

**Instructional Design and Active Methodologies in Virtual Learning
Environments: A Systematic Mapping Study**
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Abstract

This study presents a systematic mapping study (SMS) that explores trends in instructional design (ID) and active methodologies within Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs). The research followed the protocol of Kitchenham and Charters (2007), including literature published from 2010 to 2022, complemented by an update of trends from 2023 to 2025. From over 3,000 studies initially identified, 61 met the inclusion and quality criteria. Results indicate a predominance of studies addressing learning strategies, instructional design approaches, and functionalities in VLEs, with recent advances integrating Generative Artificial Intelligence for adaptive and personalized learning. The findings reveal a gap regarding the operationalization of instructional design theories in VLEs, highlighting the need for integrative frameworks that connect pedagogical strategies, technologies, and evaluation models. The mapping supports the theoretical foundation for the conceptual framework proposed in the doctoral research project, aiming to align pedagogical intentions with digital affordances in contemporary VLEs.

Keywords

Instructional Design; Active Methodologies; Virtual Learning Environments; Systematic Mapping; Educational Technology

1. Introduction

The growing integration of digital technologies into educational contexts has transformed teaching and learning practices, prompting the development of frameworks to guide instructional design and pedagogical planning. Despite numerous proposals, gaps remain in understanding how active methodologies and instructional design can be systematically integrated into Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs). This study aims to map the state of the art in this field, identifying relevant strategies, approaches, and functionalities supporting instructional design in VLEs.

Several studies have proposed frameworks to guide pedagogical planning and the integration of digital technologies into education. These works provide valuable foundations for understanding how technology-mediated learning can be designed across diverse contexts and audiences.

To ensure the contemporary relevance of this research, a complementary review (2023–2025) was conducted, focusing on intersections between Instructional Design (ID), Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs), and emerging technologies, particularly Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI). This update contextualizes the evolution of the field and highlights new perspectives on adaptive and personalized learning systems.

Prior research demonstrates varied approaches to framework development — from distributed instructional design for MOOCs (Garrido, Rêgo, & Matos, 2018) and gamified learning object modeling (Félix et al., 2023) to frameworks for game-based education (Viana, Cunha, & Alves, 2016), social network–mediated learning (Maleko et al., 2013), and pedagogical planning with digital technologies in basic education (Lustosa, 2021).

Although these contributions advanced educational design theory, most focus on specific contexts or artifacts. This study extends the discussion by presenting a

systematic mapping that identifies trends and gaps in frameworks combining Instructional Design, active methodologies, and VLEs. The results serve as a foundation for the conceptual framework proposed in this doctoral research, aimed at aligning pedagogical practices with digital affordances in contemporary learning environments.

2. Methodology

This systematic mapping study (SMS) follows the guidelines proposed by Kitchenham and Charters (2007). The mapping process was structured around the following stages: definition of research questions, search strategy, selection criteria, quality assessment, and data synthesis. Six main databases were queried (ACM, IEEE, Scopus, ScienceDirect, Springer, DBLP), covering studies from 2010 to 2022. A complementary update included works from 2023–2025 addressing recent intersections of instructional design and artificial intelligence.

Empirical research is essential to ensure the practical relevance of the educational artifact developed using the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology (PIMENTEL, 2020). According to the principles of this paradigm, the construction of a conceptual framework must be grounded in a problem, validated with concrete evidence, and refined based on theoretical and practical findings.

To comply with the DSR methodology, a data triangulation strategy was adopted, combining different sources and empirical approaches. The investigative path included: (i) a systematic mapping study, which allowed the identification of theoretical gaps and existing models in the area; (ii) a survey with elementary and higher education teachers, which brought to light perceptions, difficulties, and practical needs; and (iii) interviews with experts, aimed at critical validation and conceptual refinement of the framework.

Figure 1. Research steps.

Source: The authors (2025).

The combination of these data enabled an in-depth understanding of the digital educational context and guided the necessary adjustments to the proposed model. At the end of the chapter, the first refined version of the artifact is presented, which will later be evaluated through focus groups and practical application in a case study.

According to Kitchenham e Charters (2007), the mapping protocol specifies the methods used to perform a systematic mapping, thereby reducing the researcher's bias. With the SMS, we aim to obtain relevant works in the area to be researched, with the goal of returning references and estimating the popularity of the research area through a reliable count of the number of researched works.

For this research, the steps were described as shown in Figure 1. The research started with previous knowledge about approach strategies and VLEs, and a survey of the theoretical references in a bibliographic review. Studies in the area of pedagogical approaches and VLEs were analyzed, and it was noticed that some topics are pretty explored, for example, the use of some approaches in the construction of VLEs. However, there is a lack of consolidated knowledge about the strategies employed by learning theories in these environments.

After noticing the relevance, the need, and the lack of systematic studies on this topic, the research problem was formulated and made explicit through research questions. The general research question is, "Aiming to achieve integration, what learning strategies and approaches to the instructional design process should be considered in the development of VLEs?" The protocol to be used as a guide throughout the SMS for evidence collection was developed in accordance with the following sections.

2.1 Research Questions

The essential part of any MS is the research questions that guide the entire conduct of the mapping (KITCHENHAM; CHARTERS, 2007). Based on the research questions, one initiates the search activities and selects the primary studies that are considered relevant to the MS. The structuring of the questions can follow the set of Population Intervention Comparison Outcomes (PICO) criteria: P (population or problem), I (intervention), C (comparison or control), and O (outcomes). As suggested by Kitchenham e Charters (2007) and presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Protocol structured on the PICO model.

Source: The authors (2025).

Population	Published research on approaches for virtual learning environments.
Intervention	Research that presents strategies in the use of VLEs for pedagogical approaches.
Comparison	Not applicable.
Outcomes	Survey of strategies for VLE approaches.

According to this model, three research questions were defined to achieve the objective proposed in this protocol for the SMS. Table 2 presents these research questions (RQs) along with the reasons behind each question.

2.2 Strategy for primary study research

Systematic mapping will be conducted according to the following strategy for the research:

1. Will evaluate all returned articles from 2010 to 2022. This sample will be divided into two parts and evaluated by its responsible parties. If divergence occurs, it is necessary to discuss and reach a consensus, which may involve up to three reviewers in the discussion.
2. After performing the automatic and manual search, the primary studies were returned and went through stages 1 to 4, returning the partial results. Finally, the snowballing techniques (backward and forward) will be applied in stage 5, as shown in Figure 2. The snowballing technique used in the search strategy was the most effective approach for identifying obscure journal sources, based on the study by Wohlin (2014). To initiate the process, it is necessary to identify a significant and highly cited article in the systematic mapping study, providing a good starting point for future research using snowball sampling. It must be defined how many interactions or levels you want to perform with this technique. Once you have decided on the beginning of the research and included only the documents for the final analysis, it is time to start the first iteration, led by snowballing backward and forward.

Finally, deciding to include an article means that the entire article must be thoroughly examined before it is considered for use in Snowballing. Failure to do this will require a reversal of the other articles included as a base that will later be excluded. Therefore, it is essential to ensure inclusion before using the article for snowballing.

Table 2 Research Questions.

Source: The authors (2025).

Research Questions	Motivation
RQ1: What learning strategies are used in the literature?	The existence of the various strategies used in the teaching learning process becomes a reflection to help understand the role of didactics used in virtual environments. The need to investigate which strategies are used to create VLEs led to this research question.
RQ2: What approaches are being proposed for developing VLEs making use of instructional design?	With the increasing use of VLEs in the academic and corporate spheres as a technological option to meet educational demand, the importance of a more critical understanding of instructional design in the conception and development of these environments stands out.
RQ3: What features are available in VLEs to support RQ1 and RQ2?	How the process of functionality evaluation is carried out in VLEs is the motivation for this research question, aligning it with the strategies and instructional design used in the process.

Figure 2 Search Strategy.

Source: The authors (2025).

2.3 Execution

To run the SMS, two sets of strings were created, as described in Table 3. The construction of the search string used in the selected digital libraries followed the strategy defined by Kitchenham e Charters (2007). It identifies the main keywords from the search questions. Then the OR connector is used to combine synonyms, and the AND connector is used for alternative terms of each keyword.

The terms used to describe the structure of the search strings included learning theory, virtual learning environment, teaching-learning approach, framework, development, computation, and education.

Studies published from 2010 to January 2022 were considered. Due to the significant number of indexed studies and their relevance to Computer Science, the searches were conducted in the databases listed in Table 3. For accuracy, we chose to use each base's advanced search tools, filters, and string adaptation capabilities. After the search in the selected bases, the mapping execution (1st filter) sub-steps were followed. The exclusion and inclusion criteria were then applied. Next, the titles, abstracts, and keywords of each article were read.

The divergences that arose during the analysis between researchers, particularly regarding inclusion and exclusion criteria, were revisited in a reconciliation substage to cross-reference the divergent studies with the computer science graduate professor from the Federal University of Bahia, here referred to as the expert.

At this point, each researcher presented the reasons for accepting the article to the others. If there was consensus, the article would move on to the next phase; otherwise, it would be discarded. Next, these opinions were submitted to the experts for validation.

In the second sub-stage of the mapping execution, the introduction and conclusion sections of all the papers accepted in the previous stage were read (Figure 2). The articles whose reading of the introduction and conclusion was insufficient to judge adherence to the SMS were read in full using dynamic reading techniques, including skimming and scanning, as they did not require a precise, detailed reading of the entire text.

In cases where the divergence of opinions remained, a new round of cross-evaluation was performed. It is worth mentioning that all researchers involved in the SMS are PhD. Students, master’s level students, and graduate professors (with more than 05 years of doctoral experience).

3.2.4 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined to filter the results. These criteria assess practically the degree of the associativity of the papers obtained with the subject addressed by the research theme. The inclusion and exclusion criteria considered are listed in Table 3.

3.2.5 Quality Assessment Criteria

The primary studies will be assessed for quality based on a checklist (KITCHENHAM; CHARTERS, 2007). This step aims to extract primary studies with sufficiently adequate information for analysis and answering the defined research questions. In this phase of assessing the quality of the studies, the first step is to define the quality that will be used. Next, it is necessary to define the degree of rigor of the checklist, based on the review’s objectives and quality criteria, as outlined in Table 5.

Table 3 Survey questions concerning the Remote Teaching Modality

Source: The authors (2025).

Database	Search Strings	Total of Articles
Springer Library (https://link.springer.com)	(learning OR teaching OR teaching learning OR virtual learning environment) AND (theory OR approach OR framework OR methodology) AND (computation or education)	38

Science Direct (http://www.sciencedirect.com)	(learning OR teaching OR teaching learning OR “virtual learning environment”) AND (theory OR approach OR framework OR methodology) AND (computation or education)	141
DBLP Computer Science Library (https://dblp.uni-trier.de/db/journals/db/)	learning teaching teaching-learning virtual learning environment theory approach framework methodology computation education	35
IEEE Xplore (http://ieeexplore.ieee.org)	(learning OR teaching OR teaching learning OR “virtual learning environment”) AND (theory OR approach OR framework OR methodology) AND (computation or education)	267
ACM Library (http://https://dl.acm.org)	(learning OR teaching OR teaching learning OR virtual learning environment) AND (theory OR approach OR framework OR methodology) AND (computation or education)	1206
SCOPUS	(learning OR teaching OR teaching learning OR “virtual learning environment”) AND (theory OR approach OR framework OR methodology) AND (computation or education)	113

CBIE (Brazilian Congress of Informatics and Education)	Manual Search	1096
SBES (Brazilian Symposium on Software Engineering)	Manual Search	16
SBSI (Brazilian Symposium on Information Systems)	Manual Search	10
SBQS (Brazilian Software Quality Symposium)	Manual Search	40
WIE (Workshop on Informatics at School)	Manual Search	577
RBIE (Brazilian Journal of Computers in Education)	Manual Search	194

Table 4 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

Source: The authors (2025).

Inclusion	Exclusion
Articles are written in English only.	The article does not apply to any of the inclusion criteria
Articles published between 2010 and 2022.	The article does not apply to any of the inclusion criteria
Articles that contain the keywords in the abstract, title	Grey literature article
Articles that present approaches to VLEs	Article not available
Articles that are included in the field of computing and education	articles providing only concepts

The quality criteria were used to ensure that the set of studies ended with the most relevant ones. The studies were read in their entirety by two researchers, who worked individually, applying a score to the quality questions outlined in Table 3.5. For each defined question, a score [0.5 or 1.0] was applied, and only those that scored above 1.0 in total were entered into Table C.3 (Appendix C) of the most relevant studies, following the following criteria:

Table 5 Criteria for quality evaluation.

Source: The authors (2025).

QC	Quality Criteria	Scores
QC1	The study has an appropriate structure and is easy to understand.	1,0
QC2	The objectives and problems are well defined.	0,5
QC3	Presents selected studies for the field of computing and education.	0,5

3. Results

After applying inclusion, exclusion, and quality criteria, 61 studies were selected for detailed analysis. The results indicate three main research trends: (i) learning strategies used in VLEs, (ii) instructional design approaches for the development of educational environments, and (iii) VLE functionalities supporting learning and design. The highest publication peaks occurred between 2017 and 2020, highlighting continuous interest in digital learning environments. A literature update (2023–2025) revealed a growing role of Generative AI in supporting instructional design processes through adaptive learning, automated feedback, and content generation.

To organize and facilitate data synthesis, each primary study was categorized from the most recent (2022) to the oldest (2010). Soon after, the information will

be filled in and will inform the strategies, approaches, and learning theories used in developing and evaluating VLEs. Following the strategy for primary study research cited above, all Studies will progress through the stages outlined in Figure 2.

A web application was used to facilitate the systematic mapping, a tool designed to support researchers in conducting systematic study reviews in software engineering (GARCIA-PENALVO, 2017). With this tool, the initial process of selecting primary studies was documented for the databases: ACM Digital Library, DBLP, ScienceDirect, Scopus, SpringerLink, and IEEE Digital Library. The searches of the databases cited in Parsifal returned 1800 papers (considering duplicate articles). The manual search returned 2025 in the first phase. Figure 3.3 shows the number of papers found in each base, showing the percentage of the total. After removing the duplicate articles, 3058 works remained.

The second sub-stage of mapping execution (applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria) initially resulted in 699 accepted and 3058 rejected articles. At the end of this step, as recommended by the methodology, 165 articles remained.

Figure 3 Number of articles selected when performing the SMS.

Source: The authors (2025).

Figure 3 illustrates the number of articles identified in the initial searches after applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, as well as the final number of articles that underwent full reading and evaluation against the quality criteria.

Figure 4 presents the articles classified by year of publication. It is noted that the most significant number of publications occurred in the years 2020 and 2017, demonstrating that the theme of Learning Approaches and strategies in VLEs is a recurring subject. Another notable highlight was the evolution in the number of papers from 2016 to 2017, followed by a decline in the number of studies found in 2018 and 2019, which then increased considerably in 2020. After applying the forward and backward snowballing techniques, we identified an additional 23 published studies from 2010 to 2020, as illustrated in Figure 4.

To verify the updates of studies addressing the theme of this mapping, the researchers conducted new searches in January 2022 using the same databases and search strings presented in the protocol. Despite new findings, only the study by Silva, Rivero e Santos (2021) was added.

Table A.1 (see Appendix A) lists the titles (and authors) of the papers that refer to the strategies used in VLEs at the conclusion of the search. It should be noted that these articles were selected after full reading and application of the quality criteria. The tables are divided into five columns, each composed of an article identifier (ID), title, authors of the work, year of publication, and database.

The studies selected after the Backward and Forward Snowballing techniques are found in Tables 6 and 7. In the following subsection, the questions of this SMS will be answered using inferences built during the entire reading of the articles.

Figure 4. Number of articles selected when performing the SMS.

Source: The authors (2025).

Figure 5 Number of selected articles by year of publication.

Source: The authors (2025).

Figure 6 The number of articles selected after Forward and Backward Snowballing techniques.
Source: The authors (2025).

Table 6 Selected studies after Snowballing Backward Technique.
Source: The authors (2025).

ID	Title	Database	Year
SB56	SPARSE: A Teaching and Learning Environment for Software Engineering Based on Games and Simulation.	SBIE (Symposium on Informatics and Education)	2010
SB43	Use of NFC-based Pervasive Games for Encouraging Learning and Student Motivation	Third International Workshop on Near Field Communication	2011
SB45	Designing and Evaluating Casual Health Games for Children and Teenagers with Cancer	International Conference on Entertainment Computing	2011
SB46	A Virtual Programming Lab for Moodle with automatic assessment and anti-plagiarism features	SBIE (Symposium on Informatics and Education)	2012

SB53	Affectivity in a virtual learning environment: a study of pedagogical indicators.	SBIE (Symposium on Informatics and Education)	2012
SB81	Algo+-An app to help you learn programming	Proceedings of the Workshops of the IV Brazilian Congress of Informatics in Education (CBIE)	2015
SB94	Interfaces, usability and virtual learning environments: a heuristic evaluation of VLE ufpel	Communication School Notebooks.	2017

RQ1: What learning strategies are used in the literature?

To evaluate different virtual learning environments, pedagogical paradigms that guarantee the adequacy and quality of the educational process must be considered. These methodological paradigms give quantitative and qualitative approaches to process analysis.

Table 7: Most cited studies and their learning strategies.

Source: The authors (2025).

ID	Title	Database	Year
SF20	BrasilEduca — An open-source MOOC platform for Portuguese speakers with gamification concepts	IEEE	2014
SF01	A Predictor for PLE Management: Impacts of Self-Regulated Online Learning on Students' Learning Skills	Journal of Educational Technology Development & Exchange	2016
SF03	PLEs in Mobile Contexts: New Ways to Personalize Learning.	SBIE (Symposium on Informatics and Education)	2016
SF06	Introducing a personal learning environment in higher education. An analysis of connectivity	Digital Education Review	2016
SF16	Educational Data Mining/Learning Analytics Application Trends to Personalise Learning	IEER	2016
SF04	Applying learning analytics for improving students' engagement and learning outcomes in a MOOCs-enabled collaborative programming course	Interactive Learning Environments	2017
SF09	Applying learning analytics methods to enhance learning quality and effectiveness	AIEEE	2017
SF13	Learning Personalisation in Virtual Learning Environments Applying Learning Analytics	IATED	2017

SF39	Learning experiences design: Integration of e-learning environments	Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI)	2017
SF12	Comparative analysis of learning analytics tools to improve learning used in different learning platforms	IATED	2018
SF17	Exploring first-year students' experiences of using Moodle in learning an accounting undergraduate module at a South African University	ResearchSpace	2019
SF28	Analytics for learning design: A layered framework and tools	British Journal of Educational Technology	2019
SF30	Conceptual Framework for the Use of Building Information Modeling in Engineering Education	International Journal of Engineering Education	2019
SF07	Modeling the personal adult learner: the concept of PLE re-interpreted	Interactive Learning Environments	2020
SF34	Virtual reality and gamification in marketing higher education: a review and research agenda	Spanish Journal of Marketing-ESIC	2020

The realization of the VLE design should follow the flow of information in the different phases of learning construction. The steps that follow all the planning for a distance learning course are a fundamental factor in determining the quality of this course, as they involve identifying problems and solutions through the analysis of pedagogical strategies. To produce specific online teaching materials for characteristics and profiles of the students and teachers who will use this material, thinking about the strategies used, the design, and the stages of creation, development, and implementation, taking into account the decisive cognitive and organizational aspects of the teaching-learning situations.

According to Arbex e Bittencourt (2007), the stages of planning for a distance learning course are one of the fundamental factors determining its quality, as they identify problems and solutions through the analysis of pedagogical strategies. Moreover, the use of their teaching strategies, including the incorporation of images as a pedagogical element, highlights the need to discuss the graphic and instructional design of teaching materials.

The final studies selected totaled 61 after completing all stages of the SMS. The study by Kaunang et al. (2016) describes a Virtual Programming Lab Module for Moodle (VPLM) that provides the typical features of the component type (backup and restore, grade book integration, course restart, event control, role-based

access) but also specific features such as submission management, assessment support, and anti-plagiarism. Hernández-Leo et al. (2019) describes the relationships and interactions between educational data and learning designs in three layers: the learning experience, the learning design itself, and the community of educators.

However, in an earlier study Garrido et al. (2011), gamification is portrayed as a learning strategy. This describes the use of an overall strategy similar to others, such as PaCLan (RASHID et al., 2006). However, in this proposal, they incorporated new features, subsystems, and the use of Moodle to assess, motivate, and reward students using NFC (Near Field Communication), demonstrating the convenience of its use in developing this type of game. A game in which players use cell phones and NFC technology to interact with an open intelligent scenario (urban, university campus), scattered with augmented objects hidden with RFID tags. The game combines elements of strategy, adventure, sports, multiplayer, and location-based genres, utilizing mobile and wireless technologies.

The top 10 most cited studies among the 61 that include learning strategies are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Most cited studies and their learning strategies.

Source: The authors (2025).

Title	Year	Database	Citations	What learning strategies are used in the literature?
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A Virtual Programming Lab for Moodle with automatic assessment and anti-plagiarism features	2012	Current Research Information System (CRIS)	101	Backup and restore, grade book integration, course restart, event control, and specific features such as submission management, assessment support, and anti-plagiarism.
Analytics for learning design: A layered framework and tools	2019	British Journal of Educational Technology	92	Relationships and interactions between educational data and learning designs in three layers: the learning experience, the learning design itself, and the community of educators
LdShake: Learning design solutions sharing and co-edition	2011	Scopus	52	Creating designs based on any pedagogical approach; Problem-Based Learning (PBL; co-authoring areas support, remote community repositories, and social networking platforms.
Use of NFC-based Pervasive Games for Encouraging Learning and Student Motivation	2011	IEEE Xplore	39	Game, where players use cell phones and NFC technology to interact with an open intelligent scenario (urban, university campus, etc.), scattered with augmented objects hidden with RFID tags.

Promoting the Learning of Software Requirements Engineering through an Educational Game	2010	SBIE (Brazilian Symposium on Informatics in Education)	38	An educational game in digital media that uses playful aspects, challenges, hints, and quick feedback to the player.
Introducing a Personal Learning Environment in Higher Education. An analysis of connectivity	2016	Digital Education Review.	29	It offers a comprehensive collection of widgets (files, blog, microblogging, bookmarks, RSS, calendar, photos, videos, news, platform activity, wikis, etc.). It creates different groups with varying audience/privacy levels for students.
SPARSE: A Game- and Simulation-Based Software Engineering Teaching and Learning Environment.	2010	SBIE (Brazilian Symposium on Informatics in Education)	27	Software Engineering teaching and learning mode combines theory passed in the classroom with a practical approach, empowering the learner to make future decisions in real scenarios.

<p>PBLMaestro: {A} virtual learning environment for the implementation of problem-based learning approach in Computer education</p>	<p>2016</p>	<p>DBLP Science Computer</p>	<p>21</p>	<p>It employs the xPBL methodology, providing mechanisms to plan, manage, monitor, and document the workflow of the methodology.</p>
<p>PLEs in Mobile Contexts: New Ways to Personalize Learning</p>	<p>2016</p>	<p>IEEE Xplore</p>	<p>19</p>	<p>An mPLE (mobile Personal Learning Environment) and presents a possible framework for its design and use at the university level.</p>
<p>Applying learning analytics methods to enhance learning quality and effectiveness in virtual learning environments</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>IEEE Xplore</p>	<p>10</p>	<p>Apply LA/EDM methods to personalize learning in VLE. They use the techniques: Classification (to classify each item in a dataset into one of a predefined group of learners); Clustering (to determine the groups of students who need unique course profiling); Association rules (to discover exciting relationships between course</p>

				<p>elements used by students); Prediction (to predict the dependencies of learning usage on system content and activities); Decision trees (perform many learning analyses and can be used in various tasks such as prediction or analysis).</p>
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RQ2: How can VLEs support instructional design?

The VLE materializes educational actions, containing several functionalities and tools for interaction, administration, and support of educational strategies. Filatro (2010) states that VLEs are complex learning management environments that integrate resources and functions that support learning. Moreover, they provide a range of resources and tools, such as communication tools that allow interaction between individuals, for example, synchronous, instant communication tools such as chat and teleconferences, and asynchronous, non-instant communication tools such as mail, forum, portfolio, and bulletin board; pedagogical tools allow content delivery, assignment assessment, menu delivery, and templates; and administrative tools that allow management of enrollment, students and educators, access control, monitoring reports, and student performance, among others (FILATRO, 2010).

Designing VLEs requires understanding the most suitable media and language to present the content effectively. These spaces have tools and resources that complement formal teaching methods, providing renewed learning opportunities. Still, it is necessary to understand how to dispose of them strategically, how to create learning situations that seek to take more advantage of their pedagogical

potential and how to create links between the online environment and the reality of the students (FILATRO, 2010).

Thus, DI can help to adopt more appropriate methodologies and, concomitantly, to improve learning in these spaces. According to Filatro et al. (2019), the design expresses not only the visual aspects of a product but also its internal functions at different levels and forms. Thus, modes of sensory (colors, shapes, textures, sounds) and cognitive (language, metaphors, hypertext, conceptual maps, virtual reality) are identified.

Pino, Royo e Figueroa (2012) study provides an elementary development environment that smooths the learning curve for beginners. With that, it provides tools to support automatic and semi-automatic evaluation, including plagiarism-checking tools. All executions are performed in a separate, restricted environment to avoid security breaches when running student code. Oliveira e Santos (2016) defined the developed PBLMaestro virtual environment based on a methodology designed by N.E.X.T. (Innovative Educational Technology Inexperience), a group that combines methods and management tools through PBL.

In Sarinho (2017), LibrasZap (an instant messaging-based game for Knowledge Assessment in Brazilian Sign Language) supports instructional design with interfaces that present textual narratives of the game, followed by predefined textual questions that determine the flow of the game. In response to such questions, users generally type short, assertive sentences (e.g., "yes/no"), specific phrases (e.g., "ask for guard food"), or select options from a provided menu (e.g., "1-Action X; 2-Action Y"). Depending on the answers provided, the game has a differentiated execution flow according to the respective designed uncertainty system. It is noted that in the study by Alves, Hostins e Raabe (2019), for the framework, there are two pillars, the design of games with children and the concepts of learning and cognition, which were necessary to understand

the aspects of how they are developed from the perspective of education and the foundations of the development of learning and creativity in childhood. After this design is initially studied in terms of its student profiles, and the environment is defined based on the learning objectives.

RQ3: What features are available in the VLEs to support RQ1 and RQ2?

Among other issues, it is essential to evaluate the artifacts' functionality, i.e., if they correspond to the specification of the requirements raised and the effectiveness and efficiency of the methods, techniques, and tools used. In the evaluation phase of (FILATRO, 2010) instructional design proposal, it is necessary to review the strategies used and the solutions adopted (or designed). The evaluation needs to consider not only the student's perspective but also the tutors, as the tutor actively participates in producing the material and guiding students.

Of the selected SMS studies, among the most recent is that of Hernández-Leo et al. (2019), where his proposed framework provides a collaborative space for the functions of (co)design, labeling, sharing, exploring, reusing, and commenting on learning designs at different levels of granularity, pedagogies, and design phases, in various representations.

In Corradi e Menezes (2020), the environment includes some of the following features: a mechanism to avoid producing repeated statements in the process of generating problem situations in the additive field; having a graphical feature to help students in the similar counting process when they do it using objects; being able to record all track (mouse movement/click and keyboard inputs) during problem situation solving; generate information to help the teacher understand what kind of difficulty the student problem solving, and have a dashboard for the teacher that displays meaningful information about the student's problem-solving situations so that the teacher can capture the student and make some intervention/assistance.

In Silva, Rivero e Santos (2021), ProgramSE (Game for learning concepts of programming logic), aims to encompass the syllabus of introductory programming courses with the following features: (1) Sequence; (2) Selection; (3) Repetition; (4) Function and Procedure; (5) Recursion; (6) Vector and Matrix; and (7) Sorting.

In contrast, in the study by Costa et al. (2020), the Kalinin II system provides the following features to support the instructional design and learning strategies used:

1. Learning tracks with adaptive options, driven by an intelligent tutor, so students can choose the knowledge they are interested.
2. Adopted solving tips and support materials while performing exercises.
3. Availability of exercises tailored to the student's interests.

3.2.7 Summarizing the results

Despite using different VLEs, the articles identified in the SMS converge on several aspects. Some of the proposed tools play a crucial role in instructional design for VLE development. However, the authors report their impact only on the instructional aspect without relating their reflections on the quality of learning among students.

The studies propose computational tools and make a partial analysis of their impact. Thus, this research occurred within the framework of this justice SMS to devise a unified approach to learning strategies and instructional design.

Any computational artifact inserted into VLEs impacts the instructional journey of students and teachers. It is necessary to analyze its insertion in a unified way from the planning of the artifact. However, the investigated articles outline essential strategies for learning to design a VLE effectively, including the use of tools and instructional design functionalities.

It was observed that most of the selected studies clearly describe the learning strategies used in their VLEs and the instructional design. However, when we checked the functionalities available in VLEs to support RQ1 and RQ2, we found only 27 that indicated such functionalities, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Articles that address the features available in VLEs.

Source: The authors (2025).

The synthesis of the mapping revealed a clear gap in the literature regarding the operationalization of instructional design theories in VLEs. Most studies emphasize methodological principles or technological tools, but few provide integrated frameworks that connect learning objectives, strategies, and assessment in a coherent structure.

This gap directly informed the development of the conceptual framework proposed in this thesis, designed to bridge theory and practice by aligning pedagogical intentions with digital. Thus, the framework addresses the need identified in the mapping for a model that is not only descriptive but also applicative and adaptive, capable of guiding teachers in planning, implementing, and evaluating active learning experiences in VLEs.

3.2.8 Update of Literature Trends (2023–2025)

Complementary searches conducted between 2023 and 2025 revealed emerging themes that expand the intersections between Instructional Design (ID), Virtual

Learning Environments (VLEs), and Artificial Intelligence (AI). Recent studies (CHOI; LEE; PARK, 2024; KOZAN; STEFANIAK; MOORE, 2025; VOROBYEVA; PETROVA; LI, 2025; GIANNAKOS, 2024; STEFANIAK; MOORE, 2024) highlight the growing role of Generative AI in educational contexts, supporting automated content generation, adaptive feedback, and inclusive design.

These works point toward the evolution of ID practices into dynamic and personalized design models, in which human and artificial intelligences collaborate to optimize learning processes. This emerging direction reinforces the timeliness of the conceptual framework proposed in this thesis, which aligns with current movements toward personalization, automation, and hybrid design in digital learning environments.

The complementary literature update (2023–2025) was conducted solely to contextualize the field's ongoing evolution. The original mapping protocol, selection criteria, and data analysis procedures remained unchanged to preserve methodological consistency and reliability.

3.2.9 Threats to Validity

Potential threats to validity include keyword bias, subjective evaluation during selection and quality assessment, and limitations in database coverage. To mitigate these risks, multiple reviewers participated in selection and data extraction processes, employing triangulation and consensus-based validation. Although results may not be entirely generalizable, the systematic approach ensures methodological rigor and replicability. In this study, the following potential threats to validity were identified:

Keyword bias: the set of keywords selected in the search may not represent the domain's most representative keywords. Therefore, it may not have returned the best set of documents aimed at strategies in VLEs.

Quality assessment bias: the quality assessment and ranking of the papers were influenced by the author's knowledge and understanding. Exclusion and quality criteria were defined at the time of inclusion to mitigate this threat for the selected studies. Additionally, disagreements were discussed, resolved, and agreed upon with the assistance of the second and third authors.

Internal validity: threats to internal validity include subjective decisions that may have occurred during primary study selection, data extraction, and individual bias in the evaluation. Including a study in the analysis is the most significant factor influencing the conclusions. Given that some primary studies did not provide a clear description or adequate objectives and results, the objective application of quality criteria and unbiased data extraction were dictated. The strategy to minimize selection and extraction errors involved considering the various stages of the review to incorporate as many complete primary studies as possible, thereby increasing the reliability of the conclusions.

External validity: most of the papers included in this SMS refer to strategies used by VLEs. However, most selected studies on strategies do not refer to virtual learning environments. This prevents us from claiming that the classification provided in the present SMS is fully generalizable.

Reliability: is concerned with issues that affect the ability to design a study so that its operations can be repeated with the same results. To achieve this goal, we defined the research strings and procedures so that other researchers could directly and objectively replicate this study. However, we cannot guarantee that other investigators will achieve the same results, as subjectivity is a frequent criticism of the analysis of primary studies. As usual, the underlying trends are expected to remain unchanged.

Discussion

The synthesis of studies reveals an imbalance between pedagogical theories and their computational implementation within VLEs. Many models emphasize instructional or technological aspects in isolation. The identified gap calls for frameworks that integrate instructional design, pedagogical intentions, and digital affordances. The present mapping provides empirical evidence that supports the

design of an adaptable conceptual framework capable of guiding teachers and developers in the creation of pedagogically coherent digital learning environments.

6. Conclusion

This systematic mapping study identified major trends and gaps in the intersection of instructional design, active methodologies, and VLEs. The findings highlight the need for integrative frameworks capable of bridging theoretical models and practical implementations. The study provides a theoretical foundation for the conceptual framework proposed in the doctoral research, contributing to advancing digital pedagogical design practices.

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